

Survey details

Supplemental Material to “A Survey on Cross-Virtuality Analytics”

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1 Representative paper overview

[BSYB20]	BAI, H. et al. "A User Study on Mixed Reality Remote Collaboration with Eye Gaze and Hand Gesture Sharing". <i>Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)</i> . ACM, 2020
[BIF04]	BENKO, H. et al. "Collaborative Mixed Reality Visualization of an Archaeological Excavation". <i>International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)</i> . IEEE, 2004
[BKP01]	BILLINGHURST, M. et al. "The Magic Book: A Transitional AR Interface". <i>Computers & Graphics</i> 25.5 (2001)
[BJR20]	BUTCHER, P.W.S. et al. "VRIA: A Web-Based Framework for Creating Immersive Analytics Experiences". <i>IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics</i> (2020)
[BHM*18]	BUTSCHER, S. et al. "Clusters, Trends, and Outliers: How Immersive Technologies Can Facilitate the Collaborative Analysis of Multidimensional Data". <i>Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)</i> . ACM, 2018
[CDH*19]	CAVALLO, M. et al. "Immersive Insights: A Hybrid Analytics System for Collaborative Exploratory Data Analysis". <i>Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (VRST)</i> . ACM, 2019
[CRHG17]	CLERGEAUD, D. et al. "Towards Seamless Interaction between Physical and Virtual Locations for Asymmetric Collaboration". <i>Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (VRST)</i> . ACM, 2017
[CDK*17]	CORDEIL, M. et al. "Immersive Collaborative Analysis of Network Connectivity: CAVE-Style or Head-Mounted Display?": <i>IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics</i> 23.1 (2017)
[DDC*14]	DONALEK, C. et al. "Immersive and Collaborative Data Visualization Using Virtual Reality Platforms". <i>International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)</i> . IEEE, 2014
[ESE06]	EISSELE, M. et al. "Transition of Mixed, Virtual, and Augmented Reality in Smart Production Environments - an Interdisciplinary View". <i>Conference on Robotics, Automation and Mechatronics (RAM)</i> . IEEE, 2006
[GAWK16]	GARCÍA-HERNÁNDEZ, R.J. et al. "Perspectives for Using Virtual Reality to Extend Visual Data Mining in Information Visualization". <i>Aerospace Conference</i> . IEEE, 2016
[GDM19]	GRANDI, J.G. et al. "Characterizing Asymmetric Collaborative Interactions in Virtual and Augmented Realities". <i>Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)</i> . IEEE, 2019
[GLB05]	GRASSET, R. et al. "Evaluation of Mixed-Space Collaboration". <i>International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)</i> . IEEE, 2005
[HL19]	HUSUNG, M. and LANGBEHN, E. "Of Portals and Orbs: An Evaluation of Scene Transition Techniques for Virtual Reality". <i>Mensch und Computer (MuC)</i> . ACM, 2019
[KO97]	KIJIMA, R. and OJIKI, T. "Transition between Virtual Environment and Workstation Environment with Projective Head Mounted Display". <i>Annual International Symposium on Virtual Reality</i> . IEEE, 1997
[KTY99]	KIYOKAWA, K. et al. "A Collaboration Support Technique by Integrating a Shared Virtual Reality and a Shared Augmented Reality". <i>International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)</i> . vol. 6. IEEE, 1999
[KWFK20]	KUNERT, A. et al. "Multi-Window 3D Interaction for Collaborative Virtual Reality". <i>IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics</i> 26.11 (2020)
[LCPD19]	LEE, B. et al. "FIESTA: A Free Roaming Collaborative Immersive Analytics System". <i>International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)</i> . ACM, 2019
[MAG*16]	MEHTA, M. et al. "Active Pathways: Using Active Tangibles and Interactive Tabletops for Collaborative Modeling in Systems Biology". <i>International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)</i> . ACM, 2016
[MBHM17]	MEN, L. et al. "The Impact of Transitions on User Experience in Virtual Reality". <i>Virtual Reality (VR)</i> . IEEE, 2017
[NMT*19]	NAM, J.W. et al. "Worlds-in-Wedges: Combining Worlds-in-Miniature and Portals to Support Comparative Immersive Visualization of Forestry Data". <i>Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)</i> . IEEE, 2019
[NJ19]	NISHIMOTO, A. and JOHNSON, A.E. "Extending Virtual Reality Display Wall Environments Using Augmented Reality". <i>Symposium on Spatial User Interaction</i> . ACM, 2019
[PKP*18]	PFEIFFER, M. et al. "IMHOTEP: Virtual Reality Framework for Surgical Applications". <i>International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery</i> 13.5 (2018)
[PGW*14]	PICK, S. et al. "A 3D Collaborative Virtual Environment to Integrate Immersive Virtual Reality into Factory Planning Processes". <i>International Workshop on Collaborative Virtual Environments (3DCVE)</i> . 2014
[PLLB17]	PIUMSOMBOON, T. et al. "CoVAR: A Collaborative Virtual and Augmented Reality System for Remote Collaboration". <i>SIGGRAPH Asia (SA) - Emerging Technologies</i> . ACM, 2017
[PDE*19]	PIUMSOMBOON, T. et al. "The Effects of Sharing Awareness Cues in Collaborative Mixed Reality". <i>Frontiers in Robotics and AI</i> 6 (2019)
[PC17]	PORSSUT, T. and CHARDONNET, J. "Asymmetric Telecollaboration in Virtual Reality". <i>Virtual Reality (VR)</i> . IEEE, 2017
[PLE*19]	PROUZEAU, A. et al. "Visual Link Routing in Immersive Visualisations". <i>International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)</i> . ACM, 2019
[RJS*15]	RÄDLE, R. et al. "Spatially-Aware or Spatially-Agnostic?: Elicitation and Evaluation of User-Defined Cross-Device Interactions". <i>Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)</i> . ACM, 2015
[RH17a]	ROO, J.S. and HACHET, M. "One Reality: Augmenting How the Physical World Is Experienced by Combining Multiple Mixed Reality Modalities". <i>Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology (UIST)</i> . ACM, 2017
[RH17b]	ROO, J.S. and HACHET, M. "Towards a Hybrid Space Combining Spatial Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality". <i>Symposium on 3D User Interfaces (3DUI)</i> . IEEE, 2017
[RBCH18]	ROO, J.S. et al. "Understanding Users Capability to Transfer Information between Mixed and Virtual Reality". <i>Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)</i> . ACM, 2018
[SBI19]	SERENO, M. et al. "Supporting Volumetric Data Visualization and Analysis by Combining Augmented Reality Visuals with Multi-Touch Input". <i>EG/VisGTC Conference on Visualization (EuroVis) - Posters</i> . 2019
[SBH*09]	STEINICKE, F. et al. "Does a Gradual Transition to the Virtual World Increase Presence?": <i>Virtual Reality Conference</i> . IEEE, 2009
[SSFG98]	SZALAVÁRI, Z. et al. "Studierstube": An Environment for Collaboration in Augmented Reality". <i>Virtual Reality</i> 3.1 (1998)
[UKAG19]	UTZIG, S. et al. "Augmented Reality for Remote Collaboration in Aircraft Maintenance Tasks". <i>Aerospace Conference</i> . IEEE, 2019
[VF17]	VALKOV, D. and FLAGGE, S. "Smooth Immersion: The Benefits of Making the Transition to Virtual Environments a Continuous Process". <i>Symposium on Spatial User Interaction (SUI)</i> . ACM, 2017

The above table provides a representative selection of publications in the survey, along with their details. The choice of

this representative selection was based on being cited in at least two sections. This list is intended as a reading help for the main survey. When keeping the page containing the table open in a separate document window, it can act as a lookup table for the most common citation keys.

2 Considered journals and conferences

Here we list the journals and conferences that were investigated in detail (where in addition to the keyword search, we screened recent issues). In brackets, we give the number of papers from the respective journal or conference; the first number indicates the number of papers included in the candidate list (the combination of the lists in Section 3.1, Section 3.2 and Section 3.3), the second the number of papers in the final list of references included in the report (the combination of the lists in Section 3.1, Section 3.2, and Section 3.5, excluding the ones in Section 3.3 and Section 3.4).

Journals:

- Computer Graphics Forum [7/6]
- Computers & Graphics [4/2]
- Computer Graphics and Applications [6/1]
- Journal of Visual Languages & Computing [3/1]
- Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics [29/22]
- Virtual Reality [2/2]

Conferences:

- Annual Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology (UIST) [4/3]
- Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI), as well as associated workshops [26/25]
- Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR), as well as associated workshops [16/15]
- International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces (AVI) [2/0]
- International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR) [4/2]
- International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS), as well as associated workshops [17/12]
- International Conference on Visualization, (SciVis, VAST, and associated workshops) [7/0]
- International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR) [8/6]
- Mensch und Computer (MuC) [3/2]
- Pacific Visualization Symposium (PacificVis) [4/2]
- Symposium on 3D User Interfaces (3DUI) [5/2]
- Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (VRST/2) [5]
- Virtual Reality Conference (VR) [6/5]

3 Considered references

3.1 Papers rated core relevant (n=118)

[ACC99] ARMS, L., COOK, D., and CRUZ-NEIRA, C. “The Benefits of Statistical Visualization in an Immersive Environment”. *Virtual Reality (VR)*. IEEE, 1999, 88–95. DOI: 10.1109/VR.1999.756938.

[AV05] ANTHES, C. and VOLKERT, J. “A Toolbox Supporting Collaboration in Networked Virtual Environments”. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2005, 383–390. DOI: 10.1007/11428862_53.

- [AZPT17] AMZA, C.G., ZAPCIU, A., POPESCU, D., and TEODORESCU, O. “Augmented Reality Application for Training in Pipe Defects Ultrasonic Investigation”. *MATEC Web of Conferences* 121 (2017). Ed. by BONDREA, I., SIMION, C., and INTA, M., 04001. DOI: 10.1051/mateconf/201712104001.
- [BCBM18] BILLINGHURST, M., CORDEIL, M., BEZERIANOS, A., and MARGOLIS, T. “Collaborative Immersive Analytics”. *Immersive Analytics*. Ed. by MARRIOTT, K., SCHREIBER, F., DWYER, T., et al. Springer International Publishing, 2018, 221–257. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-01388-2_8.
- [BCC*20] BATCH, A., CUNNINGHAM, A., CORDEIL, M., et al. “There Is No Spoon: Evaluating Performance, Space Use, and Presence with Expert Domain Users in Immersive Analytics”. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 26.1 (2020), 536–546. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2019.2934803.
- [BDC*16] BACH, B., DACHSELT, R., CARPENDALE, S., et al. “Immersive Analytics: Exploring Future Interaction and Visualization Technologies for Data Analytics”. *International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)*. ACM, 2016, 529–533. DOI: 10.1145/2992154.2996365.
- [BHM*18] BUTSCHER, S., HUBENSCHMID, S., MÜLLER, J., et al. “Clusters, Trends, and Outliers: How Immersive Technologies Can Facilitate the Collaborative Analysis of Multidimensional Data”. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)*. ACM, 2018, 1–12. DOI: 10.1145/3173574.3173664.
- [BJR20] BUTCHER, P.W.S., JOHN, N.W., and RITSOS, P.D. “VRIA: A Web-Based Framework for Creating Immersive Analytics Experiences”. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* (2020), 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2020.2965109.
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- [BKP01b] BILLINGHURST, M., KATO, H., and POUPYREV, I. “The Magic Book: A Transitional AR Interface”. *Computers & Graphics* 25.5 (2001), 745–753. DOI: 10.1016/S0097-8493(01)00117-0.
- [BPRH20] BABIC, T., PERTENEDER, F., REITERER, H., and HALLER, M. “Simo: Interactions with Distant Displays by Smartphones with Simultaneous Face and World Tracking”. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI) - Extended Abstracts*. ACM, 2020, 1–12. DOI: 10.1145/3334480.3382962.
- [BPZ*17] BELLGARDT, M., PICK, S., ZIELASKO, D., et al. “Utilizing Immersive Virtual Reality in Everydaywork”. *Workshop on Everyday Virtual Reality (WEVR)*. IEEE, 2017. DOI: 10.1109/wevr.2017.7957708.
- [BRLD17] BÜSCHEL, W., REIPSCHLÄGER, P., LANGNER, R., and DACHSELT, R. “Investigating the Use of Spatial Interaction for 3D Data Visualization on Mobile Devices”. *International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)*. ACM, 2017, 62–71. DOI: 10.1145/3132272.3134125.
- [BSB*18] BACH, B., SICAT, R., BEYER, J., et al. “The Hologram in My Hand: How Effective Is Interactive Exploration of 3D Visualizations in Immersive Tangible Augmented Reality?”. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 24.1 (2018), 457–467. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2017.2745941.
- [BSE*17] BAUMEISTER, J., SSIN, S.Y., ELSAYED, N.A.M., et al. “Cognitive Cost of Using Augmented Reality Displays”. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 23.11 (2017), 2378–2388. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2017.2735098.
- [BSZ*18] BRUDY, F., SUWANWATCHARACHAT, S., ZHANG, W., et al. “EagleView: A Video Analysis Tool for Visualising and Querying Spatial Interactions of People and Devices”. *International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)*. ACM, 2018, 61–72. DOI: 10.1145/3279778.3279795.
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- [BVD19] BÜSCHEL, W., VOGT, S., and DACHSELT, R. “Augmented Reality Graph Visualizations”. *IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications* 39.3 (2019), 29–40. DOI: 10.1109/MCG.2019.2897927.
- [CBHH17] CHATZOPOULOS, D., BERMEJO, C., HUANG, Z., and HUI, P. “Mobile Augmented Reality Survey: From Where We Are to Where We Go”. *IEEE Access* 5 (2017), 6917–6950. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2698164.
- [CBL*17] CORDEIL, M., BACH, B., LI, Y., et al. “A Design Space for Spatio-Data Coordination: Tangible Interaction Devices for Immersive Information Visualisation”. *IEEE Pacific Visualization Symposium (PacificVis)*. 2017, 5. DOI: 10.1109/PACIFICVIS.2017.8031578.
- [CCB*19] CORDEIL, M., CUNNINGHAM, A., BACH, B., et al. “IATK: An Immersive Analytics Toolkit”. *Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*. IEEE, 2019, 200–209. DOI: 10.1109/VR.2019.8797978.
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- [CCD*17] CORDEIL, M., CUNNINGHAM, A., DWYER, T., et al. “ImAxes: Immersive Axes as Embodied Affordances for Interactive Multivariate Data Visualisation”. *Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology (UIST)*. ACM, 2017, 71–83. DOI: 10.1145/3126594.3126613.
- [CDH*19] CAVALLO, M., DOLAKIA, M., HAVLENA, M., et al. “Immersive Insights: A Hybrid Analytics System for Collaborative Exploratory Data Analysis”. *Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (VRST)*. ACM, 2019, 1–12. DOI: 10.1145/3359996.3364242.
- [CDK*17] CORDEIL, M., DWYER, T., KLEIN, K., et al. “Immersive Collaborative Analysis of Network Connectivity: CAVE-Style or Head-Mounted Display?”. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 23.1 (2017), 441–450. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2016.2599107.
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- [WGA*16] WURM, L., GARCÍA, R., ANTHES, C., et al. "Benefits of Tablet Interfaces for Immersive Visualization in Information Visualization". *International Conference in Central Europe on Computer Graphics, Visualization and Computer Vision (WSCG)*. 2016, 1–4. DOI: 10.5282/ubm/epub.35799.
- [WRFN18] WAGNER FILHO, J.A., REY, M.F., FREITAS, C.M.D.S., and NEDEL, L. "Immersive Visualization of Abstract Information: An Evaluation on Dimensionally-Reduced Data Scatterplots". *Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*. IEEE, 2018, 483–490. DOI: 10.1109/VR.2018.8447558.
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- [FLGL15] FALSCHLUNGER, L., LEHNER, O., GRABMANN, E., and LOSBICHLER, H. "Deriving a Holistic Cognitive Fit Model for an Optimal Visualization of Data for Management Decisions". *International Symposium on Partial Least Squares Path Modeling - the Conference for PLS Users*. University of Twente, 2015. DOI: 10.3990/2.353.
- [GOR*19] GIRAudeau, P., OLRy, A., ROO, J.S., et al. "CARDS: A Mixed-Reality System for Collaborative Learning at School". *International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)*. ACM, 2019, 55–64. DOI: 10.1145/3343055.3359721.
- [IFP*12] ISENBERG, P., FISHER, D., PAUL, S.A., et al. "Co-Located Collaborative Visual Analytics around a Tabletop Display". *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 18.5 (2012), 689–702. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2011.287.
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- [PBC17] PROUZEAU, A., BEZERIANOS, A., and CHAPUIS, O. “Evaluating Multi-User Selection for Exploring Graph Topology on Wall-Displays”. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 23.8 (2017), 1936–1951. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2016.2592906.
- [PBC18] PROUZEAU, A., BEZERIANOS, A., and CHAPUIS, O. “Awareness Techniques to Aid Transitions between Personal and Shared Workspaces in Multi-Display Environments”. *International Conference on Interactive Surfaces and Spaces (ISS)*. ACM, 2018, 291–304. DOI: 10.1145/3279778.3279780.
- [PJR*17] PLANK, T., JETTER, H.C., RÄDLE, R., et al. “Is Two Enough?: ! Studying Benefits, Barriers, and Biases of Multi-Tablet Use for Collaborative Visualization”. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)*. ACM, 2017, 4548–4560. DOI: 10.1145/3025453.3025537.
- [PLB18] PIUMSOMBOON, T., LEE, G.A., and BILLINGHURST, M. “Snow Dome: A Multi-Scale Interaction in Mixed Reality Remote Collaboration”. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI) - Extended Abstracts*. ACM, 2018, 1–4. DOI: 10.1145/3170427.3186495.
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- [RLR*20] RIEHMANN, P., LEÓN, G.M., REIBERT, J., et al. “Short-Contact Touch-Manipulation of Scatterplot Matrices on Wall Displays”. *Computer Graphics Forum* 39.3 (2020), 265–276. DOI: 10.1111/cgf.13979.
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- [SSMM98] SLATER, M., STEED, A., MCCARTHY, J., and MARINELLI, F. “The Virtual Ante-Room: Assessing Presence through Expectation and Surprise”. *Virtual Environments '98: Eurographics Workshop Proceedings Series* (1998).
- [SWKA19] SORGER, J., WALDNER, M., KNECHT, W., and ARLEO, A. “Immersive Analytics of Large Dynamic Networks via Overview and Detail Navigation”. *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*. IEEE, 2019, 144–147. DOI: 10.1109/AIVR46125.2019.00030.
- [TKK19] TADEJA, S.K., KIPOUROS, T., and KRISTENSSON, P.O. “Exploring Parallel Coordinates Plots in Virtual Reality”. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI) - Extended Abstracts*. ACM, 2019, LBW2617:1–LBW2617:6. DOI: 10.1145/3290607.3313068.
- [TTP*06] TANG, A., TORY, M., PO, B.A., et al. “Collaborative Coupling over Tabletop Displays”. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)*. ACM, 2006, 1181–1190. DOI: 10.1145/1124772.1124950.
- [WTHM01] WILDERMUTH, S., TEODOROVIC, N., HILFIKER, P.R., and MARINCEK, B. “Three-Dimensional Imaging and Virtual Reality Applications of Multislice Computed Tomography”. *Multislice CT: A Practical Guide*. Ed. by MARINCEK, B., ROS, P.R., REISER, M., and BAKER, M.E. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2001, 37–56. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-59450-2_5.
- [ZPR*16] ZAGERMANN, J., PFEIL, U., RÄDLE, R., et al. “When Tablets Meet Tabletops: The Effect of Tabletop Size on around-the-Table Collaboration with Personal Tablets”. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)*. ACM, 2016, 5470–5481. DOI: 10.1145/2858036.2858224.

3.3 Remaining candidate papers (n=116)

This is a list of the candidate papers, excluding the papers rated core relevant (listed in Section 3.1), and those that were added for specific subsections (listed in Section 3.2):

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